

LEAD AND CADMIUM CONTENTS IN THE SOIL AROUND THE NON-FERROUS METALS SMELTER "MIASTECZKO ŚLĄSKIE"

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Abstract

The zinc and lead smelter "Miasteczko Śląskie" in Miasteczko Śląskie near Tarnowskie Góry started in October 1968. Emission of duts containing heavy metals from the ore processing and smelting was the reason of contamination of surrounding environment by zinc, lead, cadmium or other metals. In the last few years emissions of contaminants during production of Zn and Pb were reduced, but some of the elements remain accumulated in upper layer of the soil. Heavy metals accumulated in soil and bound to the humic matter could be the reason of its degradation.

The investigated area covered about 66 km² around the non-ferrous metals smelter "Miasteczko Śląskie". Upper layer (0-5 cm) of the soil was taken for the measurements along transects set with a compass in the following directions: N, NE, E, SE, S, SW, W, and NW. Samples were taken starting from the smelter in the distance: 10,25,50,100,150,200,250 m, and then every 250 m, up to 3 000 m.

After drying the samples at room temperature and sieving, the concentrations of zinc and lead were measured with conventional AAS method.

It was found that the concentrations of lead and cadmium (Table) in the upper layer of the soil were higher than average level in Polish soils.

The highest contents of Pb and Cd in soil were found in a distance of about 1500 and 250 m from the smelter, respectively. It was probably due to grain-size composition of duts emitted by the smelter and local conditions of accumulation of heavy metals in the soil. The results indicated contamination of the soil environment by heavy metals in the vicinity of the smelter.

Table

Metal	Range of concentrations of metals in soil around zinc and lead smelter "Miasteczko Śląskie" [µg/g]	Concentration of metal in non-contaminated soils in Poland [µg/g]*
Lead	Range: 1.1-1024.7 Average: 443.9	Range: 5-85
Cadmium	0.44-178.7 Average: 13.1	Range: 0.01-1.6

*The concentrations of metals in Polish soils according to: Kabata - Pendias A., Pendias H., 1999. *Biogeochemia pierwiastków śladowych*. PWN, Warszawa.

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